

Study of the Effect of Influencer Marketing on Consumer Purchase Intention with Medators Brand Awareness and Brand Reputation: Organic Skin Care Products in Pakistan

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Abstract

This study focuses on investigating the relationship between influencer marketing and brand awareness and brand reputation in the organic skincare industry of Pakistan. The current study also probes the mediating roles played by brand awareness and brand reputation between influencer marketing and consumer purchase intention. A sample of 230 individuals was chosen and data was collected through the application of the convenience sampling method. After collecting the data, an analysis was performed with the help of Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software and the PROCESS Macro (Model 4) developed by Andrew Hayes (2013). Reliability, correlation, and regression analysis were carried out on the collected data for data analysis purposes. Along with these, a double mediation model (Model 4) was performed on the data to test the hypotheses included in the study. The results of the analysis showed that four of the initial hypotheses had proven to be correct with support from the data analysis. The current study not only contributes to existing literature but also widens the range of factors that can affect consumer purchase intention in the organic skincare industry. The study boosts knowledge and understanding of the variables and the relationships between them. Through this study, we aim to encourage researchers from different fields to explore the increasing trend of influencers and how they can help brands, not only in the Pakistani organic skincare industry but in other sectors as well for building up a brand and making it more well-known in the market for its products.

Keywords: Influencer marketing; purchase intention; brand awareness; brand reputation; organic skincare industry

1. Introduction

Companies find it difficult to produce engaging and appealing social media content but, influencers, on the other hand, are recognized to be experts who can develop both popular and interactive material (Atiq et al., 2022). Top influencers demand high fees for each social media post they produce and promote in exchange for their services that expand the reach of businesses, enabling them to make millions of dollars each year (McCooles, 2018). Instagram is only one of the several social media platforms that have evolved into influencer markets that provide advertisers with organic consumer reach metrics. When shopping online, consumers today desire fewer intrusive advertising messages. Consumers prefer this type of material over brand-created commercials because it is more softly styled and less overtly promotional (Campbell & Farrel, 2020). Influencers are now playing the role of endorsers as they act as a reference group to customers on whom they can exert aspirational content that is both informative and persuasive thus driving attachment (Atiq et al., 2022; Bearden & Etzel, 1982).

In the current world, it is essential for a brand to adapt to the changes that digitization has brought with it in order to survive among the numerous rivals in the market. A new avenue for brands and companies to employ technical advancements for marketing goals was offered by the growth of digital marketing during the 1990s and 2000s (Desai, 2019). Influencer marketing has long been used in business. The link that exists between the brand, the influencer, and the client may still be better understood with the help of researchers and academics (Belanche et al., 2021). Influencers can prove to be a strong promotional tool as their words and actions, delivered in the form of product reviews, online events, pre-release campaigns, and other activities, can shape and influence the way consumers think and act while interacting with a particular brand.

As more individuals start to understand the need of utilizing natural beauty products rather than those containing hazardous chemicals and toxins that can damage the skin and can result in severe diseases, the organic skincare market in Pakistan is observing significant sales. The issue worth looking into is if influencers are a trustworthy source for Pakistani consumers searching for real, secure, and eco-friendly items (Atiq et al., 2022). Influencers may increase brand awareness and spur customer response to products that people have never tried or even heard of before because of their enormous fan bases and luxurious lifestyles. This study's main goals are to assess the sincerity of influencer marketing campaigns and determine whether this group of individuals has the capability of increasing brand awareness and transforming the reputation of a brand in its industry. This research can assist businesses in employing influencer marketing to increase their market share by promoting their products to consumers through Internet channels. The goals of this study are to (1) Examine the impact of influencer marketing on brand awareness; (2) Examine the impact of influencer marketing on brand reputation; (3) Examine the mediating role of brand awareness between influencer marketing and consumers' purchase intentions; (4) Examine the mediating role of brand reputation between influencer marketing and consumers' purchase intention.

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This study was conducted in the Pakistani organic skincare market, which is significant given the rising popularity trends among consumers. As individuals have started to understand the value of using natural sources for taking care of their skin and bodies, there has been a noticeable rise in the usage and purchase of organic skincare products recently. It aims to explore how brands in this sector can use this emerging marketing concept in reaching new target markets and increasing purchase intention among existing customers. Figure 1 below shows all the proposed relationships.

Figure 1: Theoretical Framework

2. Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

2.1. Influencer Marketing and Brand Awareness

Influencer marketing is a new marketing idea that has caught the interest of many academics and industry professionals (Atiq et al., 2022). The crucial role influencer marketing plays in influencing customer behavior should be acknowledged for the enormous impact it has (Kanaveedu, 2022). The definition of brand awareness frequently refers to how consumers recognize and recall a particular brand. Brand awareness gives consumers a learning edge and influences their capacity to make decisions prior to making a purchase (Keller, 2003). The ideal technique nowadays is to use influencer marketing to raise product brand awareness since influencers already have a following that values their advice and views them as an authority in their professions (Dhanesh & Duthler, 2019). In the present era of too much data, consumers have a limited attention span and marketers are given the challenge of breaking the clutter and getting their brand noticed (Chopra, 2021). Brands may increase their exposure and successfully spread awareness among their target audience by working with well-known influencers.

The formulation of messages that are meant to be shared by influencers with the aim of increasing consumer awareness of the brand across various market groups is closely related to the influencer marketing process (Atiq et al., 2022). Brands are able to interact with groups of potential customers and engage them in networking activities with the help of influencers (Kádeková & Holieninová, 2018). Lou and Yuan (2019) created a thorough model in which they discovered evidence of how an influencer's educational material might result in the development of trust and, as a result, awareness among their audience or fan following. Brands gain a lot from social media influencers' ability to generate buzz, which tends to raise brand visibility and awareness (Uzunoğlu & Kip, 2014).

Hypothesis 1 (H1): *Influencer marketing and brand awareness are positively correlated.*

2.2. Influencer Marketing and Brand Reputation

Because public perceptions may have a significant impact on predicting an organization's performance, a brand's reputation is crucial for that organization (Fombrun, 1996). Companies have traditionally used a variety of techniques to improve the image of their brands, including product promotion, charitable advertising, cause marketing, and more recently, the employment of social media influencers (Dijkmans et al., 2015). The signaling hypothesis claims that a brand's reputation serves as a signal for either its organizational traits or goods (Kim et al., 2021). Due to social media's demonstrated beneficial and large influence in the world communication, businesses frequently utilize it to reduce consumer distrust and opposition (Bernabé-Moreno et al., 2015).

In comparison to how people respond to company-generated messaging, reviews and user-generated content on social media are perceived as having a more favorable message (Booth & Matic, 2011; Dijkmans et al., 2015; Schivinski & Dabrowski, 2014; Woods, 2016). According to Kádeková and Holieninová's (2018) study, influencers were said to have enhanced a brand's authority and credibility among a sizable audience by only sharing their experiences with others. According to Kim and Ko's (2010) research findings, social media may have a significant impact on a brand's reputation.

Hypothesis 2 (H2): *Influencer marketing and brand reputation are positively correlated.*

2.3. Mediating Effect of Brand Awareness

The ability of a consumer to recognize a particular brand is known as brand awareness (Aaker, 1991). Building customer awareness of a brand's goods and services is crucial because, according to Alkhawaldeh et al. (2017), consumers base their purchasing decisions on their brand knowledge, awareness, and experiences. Consumer brand loyalty increases as a result of increased brand awareness. Numerous brand details made available on social media and in commercials can raise consumers' brand awareness, which in turn raises their propensity to make a purchase (Hutter et al., 2013). Influencers have a huge impact on consumers' views towards a business and their decision-making. They can raise awareness of a product or brand early on and contribute to action afterward. Influencers' educational material can increase their audience's trust, loyalty, and brand recognition (Lou and Yuan, 2019).

Brand awareness is supposed to work as a mediating element between influencer marketing and purchase intention, suggesting a favorable and considerable impact, according to Priatni and Hutriana (2020). According to Dabbous and Barakat (2020), social media influences consumers' brand awareness and buying intentions through interactions with them. The research proposed by Shah et al. (2012) and this research are connected that there is a favorable relationship between brand awareness and purchasing intent. Because brand awareness influences brand choice, which influences purchase intention, consumers will buy products from brands they are most familiar with.

Hypothesis 3 (H3): *Influencer marketing and purchase intention are mediated by brand awareness.*

2.4. Mediating Effect of Brand Reputation

A brand's reputation is something that a company develops over time, and maintaining customer happiness is just one component of that process (Veloutsou & Moutinho, 2009). Additionally, it has been shown that when analyzing the new active, informed, and demanding customer, the perceptions of the product or service may have an influence on the quality of the consumer relationship (Stuart-Menteth et al., 2006). In order to understand how influencer marketing and purchase intention interact, this study examines the role that brand reputation plays as a mediating component. A company's reputation is used as a gauge of consumer trust in its products or services to affect customers' decision-making (Simamora & Celeste, 2017). Purchase intentions are a sign of customers' future plans or the possibility that their beliefs and actions would affect their purchase decisions (Kim et al., 2017; Rukh et al., 2021; Yasir et al., 2021). Expert opinions state that a variety of factors, such as influencer marketing (Furaji et al., 2013), sales promotions (Agbi et al., 2019; Akbar et al., 2020; Hanaysha, 2018; Said et al., 2019), brand reputation (Agmeka et al., 2019; Ramesh et al., 2019), and a number of others, can affect consumer purchasing decisions (Afroze et al., 2021; Mukhtar et al., 2021; Rana et al., 2021).

In addition, social media influencers have the capacity to make a compelling case that can change people's minds and behaviors (Booth & Matic, 2011). In the era of the all-pervasive Internet, influencers are a unique category of independent third parties that alter audience perceptions through platforms like blogs, tweets, and various other social media sources (Freberg et al., 2011). Percy and Elliott (2016) found that there are five decision-makers engaged in the process leading up to a choice to buy and the usage of the item or service.

Hypothesis 4 (H4): *Influencer marketing and purchase intention are mediated by brand reputation.*

3. Methods

3.1. Procedure and Participants

The industry of organic skincare products in Pakistan is new and still emerging, thus only a small population is aware of and uses organic skincare products. The data was collected from the target population of individuals between the ages of 16 and 45 who use organic skincare products. For this *Item Response Theory (IRT)* by Kline (2015) was utilized to calculate the sample size. According to this theory, the number of items in the questionnaire is multiplied by 10 respondents. The questionnaire drafted for this research includes 23 items hence the sample size obtained is 230 when 23 items are multiplied by 10 respondents. A convenience sampling technique was employed to get the questionnaire filled out by the sample unit. Under this sampling technique, individuals in geographic proximity who had used or purchased organic skincare products had been given the questionnaire for data collection purposes. In this study, individuals were the unit of analysis. The responses were collected from individuals including students, employees, and parents to study each consumer's unique purchase intention.

Our study's focus of attention is on exploring the increasing influence of influencer marketing that can help in increasing brand awareness and brand reputation, which can initiate buying intention among consumers. In order to investigate this, we will illuminate the correlation between four variables: influencer marketing, brand awareness, brand reputation, and consumer purchase intention.

In Pakistan's self-care industry specifically, relative to the production of organic products, there is limited literature on the impact and authenticity of influencer marketing as a digital marketing tool. The research design of this study is quantitative and correlational in nature to study the relation.

The study was conducted cross-sectional due to limited time and resources. For this research, data collection was conducted through an online platform. To collect the data, links to the questionnaire, created on Google Forms, were

shared with the target market. Survey questionnaires were distributed to 300 individuals for data collection, and a total of 230 responses were recorded from individuals who both use social media platforms and are consumers of organic skincare products. From the 230 responses, 221 (96.1%) respondents consisted of females, and the remaining 9 (3.9%) respondents were male. With regard to marital status 204 (88.7%) individuals were single and the remaining 26 (11.3%) were married. The respondents were between the age of 15 to 57, with the mean age being 22 years and a standard deviation of 6.13. With reference to education level, 58.7% of the respondents are graduates.

3.2. Measures

3.2.1. Influencer Marketing

Influencer marketing was measured by a 9-item scale designed by Nogori (2020). The proposed items aim to inquire about the degree of influence that influencer marketing has on consumers. A sample item from this section is “I’m more likely to try a new brand if an influencer recommends it.”

3.2.2. Brand Awareness

Brand awareness was measured by an 8-item scale designed by Tritama and Tarigan (2016). The proposed items aim to inquire about the degree of awareness consumers have regarding the brands. A sample item from this section is “Social media is good to be used as a marketing tool of company products.”

3.2.3. Brand Reputation

Brand reputation was measured by utilizing a 3-item scale developed by Veloutsou and Moutinho, (2009). The items consisted of asking the consumer about their opinion of a brand’s general reputation. A sample item from this section is “This brand is trustworthy”.

3.2.4. Purchase Intention

The measurement of purchase intention made use of a 4-item scale designed by Bolton and Drew, (1991). The items are proposed to ask consumers their intention and liking of using a certain brand. A sample item from this section is “I would intend to become brand X customer”.

All the items were measured using a 5-point Likert-type scale ranging from 1, representative of strongly disagree, to 5, representative of strongly agree.

4. Results

4.1. Data Analysis Method

The empirical data underwent a two-step statistical analysis procedure. Initially, the reliability of the scale, descriptive analysis, and correlational analysis were conducted using SPSS. Subsequently, Hayes's (2013) techniques were employed to test the proposed mediation model and hypotheses. Utilizing PROCESS Macro was considered the most suitable and recommended approach to examine the indirect and conditional effects.

4.2. Reliability of Scale

To assess the reliability and internal consistency of the items for each study variable, namely brand awareness, brand reputation, purchase intention, and influencer marketing, Cronbach's alpha (Cronbach, 1951) values were computed which recommends that all scale items possess a Cronbach's alpha value equal to or greater than 0.7 to ensure reliability and internal consistency. According to Table 1, the Cronbach alpha value of all the study variables is above 0.7 thus showing reliability and internal consistency.

Table 1: Reliability of Scale

Scales	Number of items	Cronbach's “ α ” value	Level of Reliability
1. Brand Awareness	8	0.863	“Very Good”
2. Brand Reputation	3	0.840	“Very Good”
3. Purchase Intention	4	0.901	“Excellent”
4. Influencer Marketing	9	0.846	“Very Good”

4.3. Descriptive Analysis and Correlation Analysis

The correlation analysis is conducted for initial hypothesis support to comprehend the direction and the strength of potential relationships that can exist among the variables under consideration. Table 2 shows that the relationship between influencer marketing and brand awareness is positive and significant ($r= 0.363$, $p < 0.01$), thus supporting H1. The relationship between influencer marketing and brand reputation is positive and significant ($r= 0.315$, $p < 0.01$), hence, it supports H2.

4.4. Testing Results of Hypotheses

To evaluate the theoretical model and test the stated hypotheses, we employed the mediation technique within PROCESS Macro-Model 4. The analysis was conducted using 1000 bootstrap samples, yielding a 95% confidence interval for the results. Table 3 represents the results of a simple mediation model regressing brand awareness and brand reputation as a mediator in parallel.

The results demonstrate the direct effect of the independent variable, influencer marketing, and mediator, brand awareness, which were observed to be positive and significant ($\beta=0.323$, $T=5.889$, $p<0.00$, 95% CI 0.215 to 0.431). Hence, hypothesis H1 is supported and accepted. Similarly, the results based on the direct effect of influencer marketing and brand reputation were found to be positive and significant ($\beta =0.317$, $T=5.018$, $p<0.001$, 95% CI 0.913 to 0.442) which is observed to support the hypothesis H2.

Table 2. Mean, Standard Deviation, and Correlation Analysis

Study Variables		Mean	SD	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
1.	Influencer Marketing	4.152	0.675	1			
2.	Brand Awareness	3.933	0.764	0.363**	1		
3.	Brand reputation	3.597	0.880	0.315**	0.453**	1	
4.	Purchase Intention	3.345	0.760	0.281**	0.404**	0.502**	1

Note: ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Direct Effect model						
Variable	Outcome= Brand Awareness					
	B	SE	T	p	LLCI	ULCI
Influencer Marketing	0.323	0.055	5.889	0.000	0.215	0.431
Outcome= Brand Reputation						
Variable	B	SE	T	p	LLCI	ULCI
	Influencer Marketing	0.317	0.063	5.018	0.000	0.913
Indirect Effect and Significance Using the Normal Distribution						
Sobel	Value	SE	LL95%CI	UL95%CI	Z	P
Brand Awareness	0.083	0.031	0.021	0.169	2.679	0.007
Brand Reputation	0.140	0.037	0.077	0.247	3.830	0.000
Bootstrap Results for Indirect Effect of X on Y						
Effect			M	SE	LL 95%CI	UL 95%CI
Brand Awareness			0.083	0.037	0.021	0.169
Brand Reputation			0.140	0.041	0.077	0.247

Table 3: Results of Simple Mediation Model Regressing Brand Awareness and Brand Reputation as a Mediators in Parallel

Note: n = 230; β = unstandardized regression coefficients; Bootstrap sample size = 1,000; LL = Lower Limit; UL = Upper Limit; CI = Confidence Interval.

Additionally, the mediation model was assessed using the Sobel test (Sobel, 1982), which examines whether a mediator explains the connection between independent and dependent variables. The two-tailed significance test revealed a significant indirect effect according to the Sobel test. The results of Sobel ($z = 2.679$, $p < 0.001$) were further confirmed by bootstrapping, which yielded a mediating effect of brand awareness on the relationship between influencer marketing and purchase intention. The indirect effect value of the mediating effect fell within the 95% bootstrap confidence interval of 0.021 to 0.169. These findings provide support for hypothesis H3. Additionally, the Sobel test results for brand reputation as a mediator ($z = 3.830$, $p < 0.001$) were also confirmed by bootstrapping, which yielded a mediating effect of brand reputation on the relationship between influencer marketing and purchase intention. The indirect effect value of the mediating effect fell within the 95% bootstrap confidence interval of 0.077 to 0.247. The findings support and accept hypothesis H4.

5. Discussion

The primary goal of this research is to test the validity and significance of the relationships included in the research framework created for this research. With the aid of prior research studies, the framework was created to explore the links between the variables mentioned. Survey questionnaires were used for the data collection procedure. The data analysis revealed that all the relationships included in this research are positive and significant. Based on the results it is proven that influencer marketing is positively and significantly related to brand awareness, which is the first hypothesis. This is in line with prior research conducted by Hund and McGuiga (2019) that suggests that an influencer's relevance to the brand and his or her interaction with the customers can impact how the brand's message is perceived. This shows that influencers can spread brand awareness and shape customer preferences. The second hypothesis was based on the

relationship between influencer marketing and brand reputation, which was proven to be significant and positive from the results of the data analysis. According to Wijnen (2019), using influencers for marketing purposes is an activity that is predicted to improve a brand's corporate reputation in the industry it is functioning. The third hypothesis defined the mediating role played by brand awareness between influencer marketing and purchase intention. In addition to data analysis, there is support from past research conducted by Shabbir et al. (2010), which claimed there is a positive and significant relationship that exists between the usage of social media marketing tools and the purchase intention with brand awareness as a mediator. This study explained how customers are more likely to purchase from a brand having a good image and presence. The last hypothesis, in which brand reputation mediates the relationship between influencer marketing and purchase intention, has been supported by research conducted by Simamora & Celeste (2017). The authors implore that consumers feel more confident in their decision-making processes because of the presence of a credible brand reputation. This brand reputation can be built and uplifted using influencers.

6. Conclusions

This research employed the use of PROCESS Macro (Model 4) to test the indirect effect between influencer marketing and consumer purchase intention with brand awareness and brand reputation as mediators. This research aims to investigate how brand awareness and brand reputation can act as mediators between influencer marketing and the purchase intention of consumers in the organic skincare industry of Pakistan and whether there exists any significant relationship worth discussing between influencer marketing and brand awareness and brand reputation. The primary objective of this research revolves around highlighting the importance of using influencers for conducting promotional marketing campaigns, uplifting a brand's image, and generating insightful content that can attract more customers by creating awareness among the masses about the existence of a brand and its product offerings. For the purpose of this research, data was gathered from Pakistani consumers who use social media platforms in their everyday lives and are frequent or past purchasers of organic skincare products.

The mediating and the direct relationships included here have proven to be true with support both from the data analysis of the figures obtained from the respondents and previous research studies conducted by researchers in the same field of marketing. The results prove that with the power of influencers, brands can easily create awareness among their target market can also create a positive reputation, both of which can further lead to the development of the intent to purchase. Influencers can serve as good reference groups and can spread awareness through positive word of mouth. When the brand receives more exposure, it is easily recalled and its image improves, which compels customers to consider buying from this brand when they come in contact with it.

The variables being studied, the relationships between them, and the data that supports these relationships have been defined with authentic and clear details added in this study. Past research conducted by varying academics proved to be quite helpful in explaining and supporting the relationships tested in this study and in adding a further understanding of the many concepts mentioned here. This research has helped marketers to understand how influencers have significant persuasive powers and capabilities when it comes to promoting a brand. Additionally, the results of this research have led us to believe that the use of influencers in the world of digital marketing is a new concept that has great potential worth exploiting for future planning and implementation of marketing strategies focused on social media.

6.1. Theoretical Contributions

The research explores the usage of influencers in the organic skincare industry of Pakistan hence, it will contribute to the judgments of different marketers and researchers by giving more explanation of the variables and the relationships that exist between them. A thorough investigation and detailed explanations are included here to aid in the establishment of effective understanding for future researchers and academics. The theoretical implications of this study highlight the utilization of the *theory of planned behavior* suggested by Icek Ajzen (1991). Based on the findings of this theory, marketers have concluded that consumers behave in a particular manner because of the presence of certain factors that can shape their intention to act in a particular way. Many studies reveal that an individual's closest interactions and their living environment can greatly affect their purchase decisions as compared to the effect created by traditional marketing approaches (Kempe et al., 2003). This also aligns with our research as influencers can make customers behave favorably or unfavorably towards a brand based on the content they create and communicate with their followers. Hence, the findings obtained from the data analysis are supported. This research explores how brand awareness and brand reputation can play the role of mediating variables between influencer marketing and purchase intention among customers.

The findings included here offer marketers valuable insights while selecting an influencer. While planning for a marketing campaign, marketers need to carefully evaluate the characteristics of the target market and understand their interests better. For this reason, the research can help them in evaluating how they can employ influencers for generating consumer traffic and getting affiliated with a third party of a new nature for engaging with customers and raising brand and product awareness among them. Because people spend more time on online social media networks, it is natural that they consider influencers, whom they follow, as trustworthy sources of information who can also give good recommendations (Zietek, 2016). As existing research on the use of influencers in the Pakistani skincare industry is lacking, this research will be

among the first of its kind that can add to the understanding of marketers operating in this particular sector by helping them understand the links between the variables and encouraging them to study more on how they can utilize this tool for an enhanced and fruitful advertising experience with the customers. The results of this study suggest that marketers in the organic skincare industry of Pakistan need to take help from influencers for driving brand awareness and creating a positive brand reputation, both of which can help in the development of perceptions that can lead to an increased willingness to purchase.

6.2. Practical Implications

This study provides many practical implications for researchers, academics, and marketing practitioners in Pakistan who wish to use new and improved digital marketing tools for making their brand get a bigger market share. This research also indicated that influencers can drive brand awareness considerably by sharing and creating appealing content related to the brand (Alhaddad et al., 2015). Through this research, it is suggested that marketers in the Pakistani organic skincare industry can use influencers for various purposes including making blog posts, videos, or pictures on social media channels, launching marketing campaigns, operating as brand ambassadors, and engaging with customers for product development and testing processes (Pinghelsinki, 2016).

While hiring influencers, marketers need to consider the characteristics of these individuals who will be given the important responsibility of interacting with the customers and delivering the brand message to them. These influencers must have a wide fan following, including the target market of the brand, thus allowing the message to be delivered to a diverse set of individuals. Influencer posts on social media platforms like Instagram, Facebook, Snapchat, etc., are a type of user-generated content that can positively influence the attitude of customers toward the brand (Schivinski & Dabrowski, 2014). Another key characteristic that influencers must possess is that they should have developed a positive reputation because of their honest and appealing product reviews. Influencers should be honest and excited about the products they are promoting, and the products must fit their image and style (Biaudet, S. 2017). The number of followers an influencer has is a major factor to consider while evaluating whether or not to work with them. Marketers are advised to engage with influencers, including bloggers, who have substantial followers on their social media accounts, thus allowing them to play the role of brand ambassadors (Tapinfluence, 2017).

This study analyses customer behavior which is created as a result of digital marketing practices, including influencer activities, that is an important topic to explore because of its increasing popularity among customers and brands. The findings of this research support and encourage businesses to understand customers' expectations, perceptions, requirements, and their understanding of digital marketing campaigns on social media platforms. Through this, marketers can proceed with utilizing the best class of influencers who match their brand image for increasing sales and online presence in the market. Brands need to build the image of being trustworthy, reliable, and consistent while promoting their product offerings as it can lead to building long-term relationships with loyal customers. This can be done by selecting influencers who are trusted by a great majority of the target market because of their truthful content and trustworthy product reviews. The more the customers trust a brand, the higher the probability of them purchasing from it (Ali and Alqudah, 2022).

Creating brand awareness is a real challenge in today's fast-paced world because of too much *noise*, which are distractions that can distract potential customers away from the brand message being communicated. In addition to using traditional advertising tools, including TV adverts, newspaper ads, billboards, magazines, etc., it is essential to investigate new and emerging tools, including social media advertising, and implement their usage while creating marketing strategies. Influencer marketing is a new concept, but it has been around long enough for a great number of brands to employ its usage in their advertising campaigns and marketing initiatives. Many brands have established their social media accounts to increase engagement with customers by communicating product information, creating advertisements, and promoting deals and discounts (Bilgin, Y., 2018).

6.3. Limitations and Future Directions

Like earlier studies, this research also includes certain limitations worth discussing. First, due to time constraints, this study was conducted using a convenience sampling technique. While employing this technique, data was collected from target market individuals between the ages of 16-25 who were convenient to reach out to during the course of the data collection processes. Future studies should make use of the simple random sampling technique to ensure that the data is more representative of the entire Pakistani population. Secondly, for this research, only customers who use organic skincare products were included in the sample. This is because the study wants to explore the effect of influencers in this sector. Future researchers should take a more generalizable approach and investigate these relationships in other sectors including fashion and food etc. Thirdly, while collecting data from individuals, survey questionnaires were utilized. While using surveys, there is a higher probability of respondents giving casual answers and objective responses that are difficult to interpret. For detailed and descriptive responses, future studies should use interviews, focus groups, and observation of consumer behavior so that marketers can understand the customers better and derive reliable results. Fourth, this study was conducted at a particular moment in time hence it has a cross-sectional timeframe. Future researchers should look

into longitudinal studies which will allow them to observe customers throughout longer periods and take into consideration changing preferences with time.

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